

1 Pilot-scale municipal wastewater micro-sieving and volatile fatty acids
2 recovery

3

4 Authors: Cinzia Da Ros¹, Vincenzo Conca¹, Anna Laura Eusebi², Nicola Frison^{1*}, Francesco Fatone²

5 ¹Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, Verona, Italy

6 ²Department of Materials, Environmental and City Planning Science and Engineering, Faculty of
7 Engineering, Polytechnic University of Marche, Ancona, Italy

8 *Corresponding authors: Nicola Frison Tel: +39 045 8027965, e-mail: nicola.frison@univr.it

9